

Data-Driven Multi-Fidelity Modelling of Large Aspect Ratio Wings with Distributed Propellers

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Strut-braced large aspect ratio wings (LARW) with distributed hybrid-electric propulsion (DHEP) show promise in reducing noise and emissions from aircraft, this furthers aviation sustainability and improves the quality of life of communities near to airports. However, low-fidelity models used for optimizing these configurations often neglect crucial flow physics, limiting their accuracy. The work presented explores two methods to enhance prediction capabilities: correcting the low-fidelity model using an error-based approach and developing a model solely based on high-fidelity Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) simulations. An error-based model aims to correct outputs from the low-fidelity surrogate, while a pure high-fidelity surrogate is constructed using the same samples. We evaluate both methods by predicting the performance of an untrained configuration within the training space to determine which approach more effectively predicts lift and drag coefficients.

I. Nomenclature

AoA	=	Angle of Attack	C_{L0}	=	Lift coefficient at 0° AoA
α_0	=	Zero lift Angle of Attack	$\frac{dC_L}{d\alpha}$	=	Lift curve gradient
C_D	=	Drag coefficient	$C_{D,\min}$	=	Minimum Drag
C_L	=	Lift coefficient	C_{D,α_0}	=	Drag at zero lift angle
DC	=	Drag Counts			
t/c	=	Thickness to chord ratio			

II. Introduction and Motivation

FOR several years there has been a decided effort to reduce the overall impact of aviation on the environment, aiming to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050 [1, 2]. Whilst much of the discussion has been focused on the global impact of the aviation sector, there is also a focus on local communities near to airports. In this case the goal has been to reduce noise and improve air quality specifically in this smaller environment [3, 4]. This has led to the drive for researchers to develop and explore new design concepts. One such concept is to employ the use of Large Aspect Ratio Wings (LARW) to reduce induced drag, improving aircraft efficiency and thus reducing fuel consumption and emissions [5, 6]. Furthermore, the employment of distributed propulsion – specifically distributed hybrid electric propulsion has allowed for a further reduction in drag than comparably sized single or dual propulsion methods. These concepts proved to be effective in improving aircraft efficiency with the ability to reduce emissions, noise, and reduce take-off/landing lengths – improving aircraft versatility [7, 8]. With the understanding that these technologies show promise, there has been a concentrated effort to develop a higher level of understanding of how LARW and DHEP could be integrated into a conceptual aircraft.

Before this study preliminary work had already been completed as part of an optimisation study to produce an airframe that would work within set constraints. This optimisation study relied on the use of a reduced order model based on VSPAero samples. This modelling technique was useful as a rapid design and optimisation tool to create results on the order of seconds rather than minutes if using low-fidelity tools or hours in the case of high-fidelity RANS studies. As such designers are then tasked with analysing a trade-off between highly accurate results vs time and resource cost. Methods exist to build models of potential performance by predicting performance from a set design

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space. For designers there is a valid use for the low-fidelity approach to do initial concept design and then use results to refine set design spaces and reduce the overall search requirements.

However, it then raises the question of whether this pre-established model should be discarded, or developed upon. The two approaches a designer could take would be to use a refined design space to sample from and build a new high-fidelity model to try and predict performance, or conversely use an error-based scheme that takes the difference between the low-fidelity model predictions and the high-fidelity samples then build a so-called “corrective” model that aims to rapidly emulate a high-fidelity model by adding a delta to the lift and drag coefficients. The primary notion behind this approach is that a low-fidelity model will be able to capture core flow physics, providing a valuable base that can be improved upon. As such, this study aims to compare and evaluate the efficacy of the approaches by taking several levels of sampling and comparing the accuracy of the two approaches compared to out-of-sample data as the number of training data points is increased.

III. Objectives

Given the known limitations of the initial approach that led to the creation of the low-fidelity ROM, it will be useful to compare how the low-fidelity model performs at both low and high-speeds. In terms of aircraft flight regimes and what environments would be useful for an engineer to design for; these flight speeds would correspond to take-off/landing and cruise, respectively. As such the two environments will be defined below:

Environment	Alt (m)	Pressure (Pa)	Temperature (K)	Density (kg/m^3)	Mach	AoAs ($^\circ$)
High-Speed Cruise	8000	35600	236.15	0.5253	0.6	[-5:5]
Low-Speed Take-off / Landing	1000	89880	281.65	1.1119	0.25	[-5:5]

Table 1 Flight Environment Details

This will require two comparisons of each approach- one for each flight environment. As such the overall objectives are listed below:

- 1) Simulate the optimal configuration, to determine the difference between the predicted lift and drag curves from low-fidelity predictions and the ones from high-fidelity simulations. This is done for both low-speed and high-speed.
- 2) Choose at least 2 design features that can be varied to create minimum and maximum bounds for the design space.
- 3) Populate design space with N samples and get lift and drag curves from both low and high-fidelity.
- 4) Build an “error” based model to correct the low-fidelity ROM, both for low-speed and high-speed.
- 5) Build a pure high-fidelity ROM using the same N samples, both for low-speed and high-speed.
- 6) Compare which method is more effective by trying to predict the performance of a configuration that is within the design space but not a part of the training set.

The number of design features to be altered has been set to 2 as to keep the number of total samples required to build a reliable model to a manageable number. The minimum number of samples grows with 2^n where n represents the number of design parameters, along with the AoA. As this study will aim to validate and evaluate the approach and not create a model for a conceptual aircraft, a smaller design space will be suitable.

IV. Methodology

A. Reference Aircraft

As previously mentioned, this study will aim to make use of a reference aircraft. This aircraft was a result of a preliminary global optimisation study that used the aerodynamic low-fidelity ROM as an integral part of the process. This optimisation study aimed to leverage LARW and DHEP technologies to reduce noise and emissions close to airports. As such it will be useful to conduct an analysis of the predicted lift and drag polars from the low-fidelity ROM and then compare the results to that from high-fidelity RANS. Listed below are the resulting parameters from the optimisation study:

Aspect Ratio	Wing Taper Ratio	Root Twist (°)	Rel Tip Twist (°)	Strut Twist (°)	Strut Chord (m)	t/c Root	t/c Tip
21.617	0.42	-3	-5	1.64	1.5965	0.18	0.09

Table 2 Reference Aircraft Geometry

In Diameter (m)	Out Diameter (m)	In Thrust (N)	Out Thrust (N)	In Tip Mach	Out Tip Mach	No. Props
5	3.979	5820	3550	0.59468	0.5885	5

Table 3 Reference Aircraft Propeller Parameters

The aircraft CAD model resulting from these parameters is presented below; with the propellers represented by 2D disk surfaces in the relevant locations:

Fig. 1 Reference aircraft generated from low-fidelity optimisation study

This aircraft uses the Airbus A320 wing area of $122.4m^2$ to determine the design of the wing, using a fixed area along with the parameters in Table 2 allows for a full definition of the wing. Along with the use of the reference aircraft, it would be beneficial to use the same geometric parameter bounds as the low-fidelity optimisation study. This would ensure that the parameter ranges that will be later used for the comparison would lead to physically feasible and sensible designs.

Parameter Title	Upper Bound	Lower Bound
Aspect Ratio	25	15
Wing Taper Ratio	0.33	0.31
Root Twist (Degrees)	3	-3
Relative Tip Twist (Degrees)	1	-5
Strut Twist (Degrees)	3	-3
Strut Chord (m)	1.597	0.906
t/c Root	0.18	0.12
t/c Tip	0.14	0.09

Table 4 Reference Aircraft Geometry Parameter Space

There are some design parameters where the geometry described in Table 2 already sits at one of the bounds of the design space. In this special case, the central value will be used as a point for simulation and/or testing.

B. VSPAero

VSPAero is the foundation for the low-fidelity ROM. It is a well-established software package that allows for the simulation of aircraft designs. Instead of high-fidelity RANS or lower fidelity Euler simulations, VSPAero employs a vortex-lattice method (VLM) with further capabilities to improve accuracy. The VLM approach uses a lattice of horseshoe vortices to predict the pressure on the wing surface and is based on potential flow theory. As such VLM makes several assumptions regarding the flow that may limit the accuracy of results.

- 1) The fluid flow is incompressible
- 2) The fluid flow is inviscid
- 3) The fluid flow is irrotational

As such VSPAero results may deviate significantly compared to CFD results. However VSPAero does not solely rely on VLM, the use of panel methods are also included to model flow effects due to aerofoil thickness and estimations of parasite drag. [9]

C. RANS Simulation

To complete the high-fidelity simulations, Stanford University Unstructured (SU2) is used to complete steady RANS simulations. In this case, the one-equation Spalart-Allmaras (SA) model is used and the second order Jameson-Schmidt-Turkel (JST) scheme is used for discretising convective fluxes. [10]

The meshing of the aircraft configuration involves primary generation of an inviscid mesh via the use of the open-source software GMSH. This software provides a fully tetrahedral mesh that is fine enough to properly resolve wing and fuselage curvature whilst allowing mesh sizing to be controlled across the domain, preventing unnecessarily detailed mesh in the far field [11]. Once the inviscid mesh has been created, a hybrid boundary layer utilising both tetrahedral and prismatic elements is inserted via the advancing normal method to generate the boundary layer to create the viscous mesh [12]. For all cases, an appropriate first cell height is estimated, and an appropriate layer growth rate is chosen to ensure that the boundary layer mesh is appropriate to capture the fluid boundary layer.

D. Actuator Disk

The aerodynamic effects of the DHEP system are modelled via the Actuator Disk method. This involves defining the propeller positions, radii, and advance ratios, along with thrust and power coefficients per unit radius. Within the SU2 solver, propellers are modelled by proving momentum and pressure increase directly downstream of the selected surface elements. Rather than applying the properties to an internal boundary face, the forces are applied directly to refined regions that were generated as part of the inviscid meshing process. These forces are applied as such

$$F_a(\bar{r}) = \frac{2\rho_\infty V_\infty^2}{J^2\pi\bar{r}} \left(\frac{dC_T}{d\bar{r}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where ρ_∞ is the free-stream density; V_∞ is the free-stream velocity; J is the advance ratio; C_T is the coefficient of thrust; and \bar{r} is the radial coordinate. $F_a(\bar{r})$ is the force per unit area, which is equivalent to the static pressure jump across the disk.

E. Mesh Adaptation

To ensure accurate results and to maintain computational efficiency several levels of mesh adaptation are used to ensure that relevant flow features are properly captured. The alternative to utilising mesh adaptation would be to utilise progressively finer and finer mesh options until the solution is grid converged. This method is just as effective when it comes to ensuring that solutions are grid-independent, however, this untargeted approach will lead to mesh sizes that would be impractically larger. This would lead to a massively increased computational cost and would impact the range and/or number of parameters that could be explored as part of a design study. The use of mesh adaptation aims to solve this by taking a suitably refined initial mesh and results in resizing the mesh, inserting, moving, and deleting mesh points where necessary. [13]

Fig. 2 Resulting Meshes: Un-adapted (Left) and Adapted (Right)

The meshes above in Figure 2 are an example of a single level of mesh adaptation on a viscous mesh of the reference case at cruise conditions flying at an AoA of 0° . It can be seen how the mesh refinement has refined the mesh in areas deemed important, such as the wake region. Subsequent levels of adaptation can be performed to further refine the mesh until a suitable detail is reached.

V. Preliminary Results

With the methodology clearly defined, simulations have been conducted to properly compare the predictions made by the low-fidelity ROM and RANS simulation results. The results of this initial investigation are detailed here

A. Reference Aircraft in Cruise

Fig. 3 Reference Case Comparison for RANS and ROM at Cruise: Lift Curve (Left), Drag Curve (Right)

AoA	C_L	C_D	DC	C_{LROM}	C_{DROM}	DC ROM	dC_L	d DC
-5	-0.29244	0.110644	1106.44	-0.80934	0.032933	329.33	0.516897	777.11
-2.5	-0.27074	0.072928	729.28	-0.43084	0.02215	221.50	0.160104	507.78
0	-0.10204	0.045327	453.27	-0.05235	0.016522	165.22	0.049688	288.0498
2.5	0.217541	0.034699	346.99	0.326138	0.016049	160.49	0.108597	186.50
5	0.574166	0.038331	383.31	0.70463	0.020731	207.31	0.130464	176.00

Table 5 RANS Simulation and ROM Predictions Results - Cruise

Using these curves the following aerodynamic values were calculated

Cruise	α_0	C_{L0}	$\frac{dC_L}{d\alpha}$	$C_{D, \min}$	C_{D, α_0}
RANS	0.800296	-0.1082	0.1352	0.0461	0.0410
ROM	0.346103	-0.0524	0.1514	0.0165	0.0161
Delta	0.454193	0.0558	0.0162	0.0296	0.0249

Table 6 Cruise Variables From Fitted Curves

The lift curve presented shows a deviation from the linear trend at the negative AoAs. Therefore the flow is inspected further to try and visualise regions that show higher complexity.

Fig. 4 Reference Case Flow Features at Cruise: -5 Degrees (Left), -2.5 Degrees (Right)

B. Reference Aircraft in Take-off/Landing

Fig. 5 Reference Case Comparison for RANS and ROM at Low-Speed: Lift Curve (Left), Drag Curve (Right)

AoA	C_L	C_D	DC	C_{LROM}	C_{DROM}	DC ROM	dC_L	d DC
-5	-0.53631	0.065674	656.74	-0.83704	0.033637	336.37	0.300725	320.37
-2.5	-0.32506	0.039492	394.92	-0.4456	0.022709	227.09	0.120542	167.83
0	-0.03024	0.030235	302.35	-0.05416	0.01714	171.40	0.023925	130.95
2.5	0.296103	0.030562	305.62	0.337279	0.01693	169.30	0.041176	136.32
5	0.620544	0.034986	349.86	0.728718	0.022078	220.78	0.108174	129.08

Table 7 RANS Simulation and ROM Predictions Results - Low-Speed

Using these curves the following aerodynamic values were calculated:

Low-Speed	α_0	C_{L0}	$\frac{dC_L}{d\alpha}$	$C_{D, \min}$	C_{D, α_0}
RANS	0.229647	-0.0299	0.1302	0.0301	0.0285
ROM	0.346105	-0.0542	0.1566	0.0171	0.0167
Delta	0.116458	0.0243	0.0264	0.013	0.0118

Table 8 Low-Speed Variables From Fitted Curves

As before, the flow features of the negative AoAs are visualised here:

Fig. 6 Reference Case Flow Features at Low-Speed: -5 Degrees (Left), -2.5 Degrees (Right)

C. Modifications

With the completion of the first series of simulations of the reference aircraft the first parameter change was chosen and simulated. The following results show the aircraft with a modified strut twist. As seen in Table2 the strut had a twist of 1.64° . As according to the previous parameter space new values of -3° in the minimum case and 3° in the maximum case were run at the low-speed condition. The results of which are seen below.

1. Strut Twist Lower Bound

Fig. 7 Lower Bound Comparison for RANS and ROM at Low-Speed: Lift Curve (Left), Drag Curve (Right)

AoA	C_L	C_D	DC	C_{LROM}	C_{DROM}	DC ROM	d C_L	d DC
-5	-0.56489	0.075082	750.82	-0.9886	0.034509	345.09	0.423705	405.73
-2.5	-0.41468	0.03812	381.20	-0.59339	0.022139	221.39	0.178706	159.81
0	-0.11866	0.02774	277.40	-0.19818	0.015202	152.02	0.079521	125.38
2.5	0.209934	0.026885	268.85	0.197026	0.013698	136.98	0.012908	131.87
5	0.537753	0.03012	301.20	0.592234	0.017626	176.26	0.054481	124.94

Table 9 RANS Simulation and ROM Predictions Results - Lower Bound Low-Speed

Lower Bound	α_0	C_{L0}	$\frac{dC_L}{d\alpha}$	C_D, \min	C_D, α_0
RANS	0.902513	-0.1185	0.1313	0.0239	0.0267
ROM	1.253637	-0.1982	0.1581	0.0137	0.0152
Delta	0.351124	0.0797	0.0268	0.0102	0.0115

Table 10 Lower Bound Variables From Fitted Curves

2. Strut Twist Upper Bound

Fig. 8 Upper Bound Comparison for RANS and ROM at low-speed:: Lift Curve (Left), Drag Curve (Right)

AoA	C_L	C_D	DC	C_{LROM}	C_{DROM}	DC ROM	dC_L	d DC
-5	-0.49069	0.072413	724.13	-0.79588	0.033669	336.69	0.30519	387.44
-2.5	-0.29533	0.038977	389.77	-0.40611	0.023245	232.45	0.110786	157.32
0	0.001209	0.03077	307.7	-0.01634	0.018059	180.59	0.017553	127.11
2.5	0.328461	0.031632	316.32	0.373426	0.018109	181.09	0.044965	135.23
5	0.652505	0.036515	365.15	0.763197	0.023397	233.97	0.110692	131.18

Table 11 RANS Simulation and ROM Predictions Results - Upper Bound Low-Speed

Upper Bound	α_0	C_{L0}	$\frac{dC_L}{d\alpha}$	$C_{D, \min}$	C_{D, α_0}
RANS	-0.01305	0.0017	0.1303	0.0298	0.0298
ROM	0.104554	-0.0163	0.1559	0.0181	0.0180
Delta	0.117601	0.018	0.0256	0.0117	0.0118

Table 12 Upper Bound Variables From Fitted Curves

D. Low-Speed Results Comparative Graphs

Fig. 9 Lift Curve of All Low-Speed Simulations

Fig. 10 Set Angle Drag Count Variation with Strut Twist

VI. Current Results Discussion and Future Work

The preliminary results have been useful in identifying the key limitations of the low-fidelity ROM's ability to predict performance when compared to the RANS simulation results. This is evident in the low-speed simulations, but especially so for the cruise simulations. The ROM consistently underpredicts the resulting lift coefficient, and severely underpredicts the drag coefficient. Furthermore, the ROM in its current state is completely unable to predict the onset of stall as it assumes that lift will progress linearly, whilst this is not the case from observing Figures 3 and 5. All of this leads to severe inaccuracies when trying to predict key aerodynamic variables for the reference case, as illustrated in Tables 6 and 8. If this ROM were solely used to design an aircraft configuration, the resulting aircraft would not perform as planned.

When investigating the flow field some of the sources of error becomes apparent. Figure 4 shows regions of separation in blue and supersonic flow in red for the -5 and -2.5 AoAs where the deviation from the prediction is at its worst. It is seen that a significant portion of the wing and strut are experiencing flow features that the ROM is unable to predict due to the limits of the training data it was provided. This would explain the significant differences between results at these AoAs. This is further supported by the results from the low-speed analysis, whilst the lift curve is

non-linear at -5 and -2.5, it is not as severe as the cruise case. As seen from Figure 6, the size of the flow regions that the ROM cannot account for is far smaller than that of the cruise case. There are only small, localised regions of separation being initiated by the propellers and no supersonic regions present. This results in a lower overall error between the ROM and RANS; however, the error is still significant and will impact on conceptual aircraft design.

As such it has been proven that the low-fidelity ROM is mostly limited to preliminary conceptual design refinements and would be ineffective for deeper design space refinements or optimisation studies where the accuracy of the aerodynamics of the aircraft is essential. This is where the comparison of a multi-fidelity approach vs a pure high-fidelity ROM approach becomes essential. A series of simulations were conducted to see how both the simulation results and error in the ROM predictions would vary when a single variable was unconstrained, and subsequently ran in the low-speed environment. The logic is that the cruise environment is one where complex flow features are already highly present, therefore by running in the low-speed environment any errors caused by a drastic increase in flow complexity would immediately be evident from the resulting lift and drag curves. For the first series of simulations, the strut twist was altered and set to the previously mentioned values.

From the results for both the lower and upper bound simulations, the strut twist is still able to influence the lift and drag results to a degree even in low-speed conditions. A variation between the errors is noticed in both Table 9 and 11 as no two AoAs show the same error. This non-linear behaviour is promising as a potential candidate for a corrective model to be considered rather than a simple addition being made to the lift and drag predicted values. However, drag variation as the strut angle changes would be useful to investigate. This is what Figure 10 shows. This isolation shows that the impact that the change in strut twist angle is highly dependent on the AoA.

Fig. 11 Normalised Drag For Each AoA

AoA, Degrees	Straightness Index
-5	0.4991
-2.5	0.6388
0	0.9260
2.5	0.9906
5	0.9522

Table 13 Straightness Index of Normalised Curves

Figure 11 is a normalised plot of Figure 10, this better illustrates the impact of strut twist for each AoA. For each AoA, it was deemed important to find a way to evaluate the linearity of the resulting curve. This is important to ensure the robustness of the comparison between approaches. To ensure that the behaviour is suitably non-linear the straightness index is listed in Table 13. The straightness index is defined as the ratio between the length of the line connecting the endpoints of the curve, compared to the true length of the curve. Curves with a value closer to 1 are more

linear, whilst lower values indicate more non-linear behaviour. The strut twist shows high degrees of non-linearity for the negative AoAs, but shows far more linear behaviour for the positive angle of attack. Given that the more non-linear the impact the harder a parameter is to model – it would be advantageous to analyse which parameter is predicted to have the most non-linear behaviour. As such the future work planned is to:

- Conduct a sensitivity analysis on the parameters indicated in Table 4 under the low-speed conditions. Analysing the straightness index for each of the resulting normalised curves.
- Choose the two parameters that show the most non-linear behaviour
- Sample the design space for at least 3 different levels of sample size, running each sample for the low-speed condition and the cruise condition
- Build two types of predictive models: one that solely relies on the RANS results as training data, and another that takes the error between the RANS results and the ROM predictions as training data.
- Compare the performance between the two models for all training sample sizes, investigating the accuracy of each model when it comes to predicting out of sample RANS results. Furthermore, investigating how the predictions improve as sample size increases.

Finally, there are a variety of techniques that can be used to build the two models. The method determined to be most appropriate in this case is kriging. This is partially thanks to the low dimensionality of the parameter space that will be investigated. Limiting the study to two parameters and AoA will lead to the samples only being three dimensional, a number that the kriging process will be able to manage. [14]

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